

**Career management strategies among IT professionals in offshore outsourced IT
firms in Sri Lanka**

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Purpose- To explore career management strategies used by IT professionals full-time employed in offshore outsourced IT firms in Sri Lanka; and to evaluate those against hierarchical plateau, job content plateau, firm size, and individual demographic characteristics that may predict the use.

Design/methodology/approach- Survey methodology was used and a random sample of 119 IT professionals responded. Multiple regression was used for the data analysis.

Findings- Career management strategies used by IT professionals could be broadly categorised into four areas. Hierarchical career plateau and age significantly predict the use of career strategies.

Originality/value- The study provides useful information for both practitioners and academics to better understand career strategies used by IT professionals in managing their own careers and factors that predict the use of career strategies.

Key words: career management strategies; hierarchical plateau; job content plateau; offshore outsourcing.

Paper: Research paper

Introduction

The employment landscape is undergoing changes. Globalisation, new technologies, demographic shifts and also the emergence of new occupations have important implications for career management (Reitman and Schneer, 2003; Baruch, 2003). There is an increasing interest on the careers of information technology (IT) professionals over the last few years. The growing interest stems, in part, from the recognition that IT professionals are a relatively scarce form of labour characterised by high level of turnover (Ituma and Simpson, 2006). On the other, in the knowledge intensive sectors,

economic value is found more in intangibles and less in tangibles. Therefore, knowledge and expertise IT professionals possess is perceived as vital to the success in the knowledge based economy (Powell and Snellman, 2004). Therefore, in the knowledge based economic sectors managing employees' careers is also identified as very important (e.g. Appelbaum et al., 2002).

IT professionals were identified to have a strong need for growth and personal development compared to professionals in other occupations (Lee, 2002). However, scholars suggest difficulties in getting career plans for IT professionals materialize in the rapidly changing IT industry (Lee, 2002). Further, the high rate of turnover among IT professionals implies that the traditional concept of an organizational career may no longer be valid and that IT professionals are likely to be actively engaged in planning their own careers (Lee, 2002, p.6). Furthermore, contemporary literature on career management suggests that the notion of career management has moved beyond organisations to focus on more flexible and individual models (e.g. Hall, 2004). Despite the increased focus on individuals' ability to manage their careers, relatively little empirical research has investigated determinants of career management strategies (e.g. Guthrie et al, 1998; Lee, 2002). Further, although literature highlights the importance of exploring career systems in different parts of the world (Budhwar and Baruch, 2003), relatively little empirical research has investigated career issues outside the Western world (eg., Baruch and Budhwar, 2006; Lee, 2002; Ituma and Simpson, 2006). Furthermore, majority of those studies confined to investigate organisation led career management practices (e.g. Budhwar and Baruch, 2003; Baruch and Budhwar, 2006). Therefore, an investigation into individual led career management strategies used by IT professionals in offshore outsourced IT firms (OOITF) in Sri Lanka appear to be a candidate for increased empirical attention.

During the past decade there is a growing tendency of Western countries to offshore outsource various IT work to other countries, especially to Asian developing countries with sufficient infrastructure and skilled human resource at a lower cost. Sri

Lanka has a young and growing pool of IT professionals. The total IT workforce in the IT industry is slightly over 30,000 (SLICTA, 2007). Over 45% of them have a degree or a higher qualification in IT, and they mainly engaged in knowledge process outsourcing services (SLICTA, 2007). They could be identified as one of the critical resources of the country in its quest to become a technologically advanced nation. Although OOITF have created a type of jobs not existed in the country before, these firms have about two layers in the organizational hierarchy- top management and technical specialists; opportunities available for promotion are few and far between (Wickramasinghe, 2009). Hence, it could be argued that a career in OOITF does not offer a well-defined hierarchical career path and that career issues faced by IT professionals are different, where the context of OOITF may shape the career patterns exhibited by them.

In the above context, the objectives of this research are 1) to explore career management strategies used by IT professionals in OOITF in Sri Lanka; and 2) to evaluate those against career plateau (hierarchical plateau and job content plateau), organisational characteristics (firm size), and individual demographic characteristics (age, gender, and marital status) that may predict the use. In order to provide the context for the article, in the next section, relevant literature is briefly reviewed. This is followed by the methodology adopted. Thereafter, the main findings are presented and discussed. The article concludes with a discussion on the implications of the findings and research areas for further inquiry and understanding.

Theoretical background and hypotheses

Career management and career management strategies

The widely-accepted conceptualisation of career is that of Hall (1990) who defines a career as a sequence of related work experiences and activities, directed at personal and organizational goals, through which a person passes during his or her lifetime, that are partly under their control and partly under that of others. Four distinctive features of this conceptualisation are: it has a long-term perspective, extending beyond the current

satisfaction and performance of employees; focuses on objective aspects as well as on subjective aspects of career; it views career effectiveness not only as something that consist of attaining socially-sanctioned positions or ranks, but also of realising goals that are personally important to the individual; and explicitly recognises that career outcomes are the joint result of individual efforts and of outside forces over which the individual does not have complete control (Orpen, 1994, p.27).

This notion of joint responsibility in career management assumes that the counterpart to organisational career management is individual career management. That is personal efforts made by individuals to advance their own career goals which may or may not coincide with those that their organisations have for them (Orpen, 1994, p.28). Further, contemporary scholars are suggesting that the responsibility for managing and developing careers has become much more a personal quest than an organisational one (e.g. Whymark and Ellis, 1999; Parry and Proctor-Thomson, 2003). Hence, individuals have to display career resilience and participate in the management of their own careers to make themselves employable (Waterman et al., 1994).

Career strategies are one of the important aspects of individual career management (Aryee et al., 1993; Gould and Penley, 1984). Gould and Penley (1984) defined career management strategies, as “behaviours which may be utilised by an individual to decrease the time required for and uncertainty surrounding the attainment of important career objectives” (p.244). Career management strategies encompass a range of employee behaviours such as networking, attempts to develop critical expertise, seeking career guidance from an experienced person, and engaging in self-nomination (Gould and Penley, 1984; Osnowitz, 2008). Extant literature highlights the importance of career management strategies in promoting career success (Gould and Penley, 1984; Osnowitz, 2006).

Career plateau

One of the variables considered in this research to predict the use of career management strategies is career plateau. When career is seen as a movement within an organization comprising both hierarchical and task-oriented movements, career plateau is the lack of such a movement (Nachbagauer and Riedl 2002). It is valid to express hierarchical career plateau as the point at which future career mobility is in reasonable doubt because the length of time in the present position has been unduly prolonged (Veiga, 1981). In the common pyramid-shaped organization, virtually everyone's career at one time or another reaches a point where further hierarchical advancement is unlikely. However, when firms rely on flat organisational structures further advancement within the organization becomes more unlikely, and employees have to face the fact that they have to stay in the same position longer than expected (Nachbagauer and Riedl, 2002).

Extant literature defines two measures of hierarchical plateau as objective and subjective measurement (Gould and Penley, 1984; Nachbagauer and Riedl 2002). Objective hierarchical plateau relied on the length of an employee's tenure in the current job (Gould and Penley, 1984; Veiga, 1981). Although job tenure does not directly assess whether an individual has reached a plateau, it appears reasonable to assume that a long time in one position indicates limited prospects for upward mobility (Nachbagauer and Riedl 2002). Hence, the objective aspect of career plateau is determined by past decisions (Nachbagauer and Riedl 2002). Subjective measurement of hierarchical career plateau, on the other hand, relies on the self-assessment of chances for promotion and it is driven by future expectations at work (Nachbagauer and Riedl 2002; Jung and Tak, 2008). It is suggested that these two dimensions of hierarchical career plateau are independent of each other (Chao, 1990; Chay et al., 1995; Trembley and Roger, 1993). However, both subjective and objective dimensions of the concept of hierarchical career plateau take as their starting point- the immobility

stemming from- the common structure of organisations, the pyramid (Nachbagauer and Riedl 2002).

The absence of new, challenging and varied tasks without possibilities of improvement or learning (i.e., lacking challenge in one's job) is called "job content plateau" (McCleese and Eby, 2006). Although it is said that hierarchical plateau may result in job content plateau, yet, it is not a necessary consequence (Nachbagauer and Riedl, 2002). As a distinct form of career plateau, job content plateau has little empirical attention (e.g. Appelbaum and Santiago, 1997; Chao, 1990; McCleese and Eby, 2006). However, in the current business climate, understanding job content plateau seems particularly important.

Given the empirical evidence (e.g. Gould and Penley, 1984) that indicates career plateau predicts the use of career management strategies, it is proposed that employees faced with hierarchical and job content plateau may use a high level of individual initiated career management strategies. Therefore, hypotheses for the study are:

Hypothesis 1: Hierarchical plateau will be significantly positively related to the use of career management strategies.

Hypothesis 2: Job content plateau will be significantly positively related to the use of career management strategies.

Individual demographic and firm characteristics

Past research has shown that individual demographic and firm/industry characteristics may predict the use of career management strategies (e.g. Gould and Penley, 1984; Guthrie et al., 1998). For instance, gender (Gould and Penley, 1984), age (Guthrie et al., 1998), personality (Guthrie et al., 1998), and the nature of industry (Gattiker and Larwood, 1988) were found to bear relationships with the use of career management strategies. However, the available information in this regard is very limited and can not be generalised. Given the empirical and anecdotal evidence that indicate those are

associated with the use of career management strategies, it is proposed that firm size (measured in terms of number of employees), gender, age, and marital status may predict the use of career management strategies.

However, as literature on careers of employees in offshore IT outsourcing context is scarce, it is difficult to find an established framework or much information on individual demographic factors that predict the use. Therefore, hypotheses for this study are developed based on the insight gained from available literature on OOITF in Sri Lanka (such as Wickramasinghe, 2009; Wickramasinghe and Kumara, 2009, 2010). First, although Guthrie et al. (1998) did not find differences by gender in the use of career management strategies, it is hypothesised that males will be using career management strategies than females as Wickramasinghe (2009) suggests that females are less satisfied with their jobs and feel a loss of interest in IT jobs in OOITF but wish to remain in the present workplace. Therefore, it is hypothesised:

Hypothesis 3: The extent of use of career management strategies by males will be significantly more than females.

Guthrie et al. (1998) found differences by age in the use of career management strategies, where older employees are more likely to maintain greater career flexibility. Further, Sri Lankan literature on OOITF reports some differences in employee capabilities by age, where older employees scoring more on their capabilities (e.g. Wickramasinghe and Kumara, 2009). Therefore, it is hypothesised:

Hypothesis 4: Age will be significantly positively related to the use of career management strategies.

Further, Sri Lankan literature on OOITF reports some differences in work-related aspects by marital status, where single employees scoring more on the positive side of employment (e.g. Wickramasinghe and Kumara, 2009, 2010). Therefore, it is hypothesised:

Hypothesis 5: The extent of use of career management strategies by single employees will be significantly more than married employees.

Although organisational characteristics such as firm size are important contextual variables, it is very rare to find studies conducted on those in relation to career management in the Western context or OoITF in Sri Lanka. However, assuming that when the number of employees in the workplace is higher, they will have more interactions leading to a higher level of use in career management strategies, it is hypothesised:

Hypothesis 6: Number of employees in the firm will be significantly positively related to the use of career management strategies.

The framework developed for the study is shown in Figure 1.

Take in Figure 1

Method

Sample

The study was carried out using a survey-based approach. A random sample of IT professionals with/or equal to degree-level education who are primarily engaged in the creation and provision of IT capacity was selected from the list of 36 firms that were registered under Board of Investment of Sri Lanka (BOI), which is the government authority responsible for identifying, promoting and facilitating export-oriented business operations in the country through both foreign and local investments. Further, it is compulsory by BOI Act (No.4 of 1978) that all BOI registered firms should export at least 90 percent of their output. Of the 300 self-administered questionnaires distributed, a total of 119 usable responses resulted in 40 per cent response rate.

Of the 119 respondents, 37% was female and 63% was male. 43% was single and 57% was married. The mean age was 31 years. 27% had postgraduate degrees; 67% had Bachelor's degrees; 6% had professional qualifications such as BCS, ACS,

and PMP. The average number of years of service in the present job was 4.17. The average number of full-time employees in the present workplace was 455. Overall, it is observed that the sample characteristics of the current study do not show deviation from the characteristics of employees in OOITF depicted in Wickramasinghe (2009) and SLICTA (2007).

Measures

Career management strategies. In generating the list of strategies to be considered for the study, the methodologies adopted by previous research were studied (such as Baruch and Budhwar, 2006; Gould and Penley, 1984; Lee, 2002). The review of literature revealed that some researchers build their lists by drawing from previous research (e.g. Lee, 2002) while some others have developed their own lists following a certain procedure (e.g. Gould and Penley, 1984). Parallel to the review of literature, we did a preliminary investigation into individual led career management strategies used in the selected industry; we have not found previous studies conducted on career management strategies in the selected industry or in Sri Lanka. After comparing the lists of strategies generated from the preliminary investigation and extant literature, it was decided to use the 25-item list of Gould and Penley (1984) as it has much resemblance to the Sri Lankan context.

Respondents were requested to indicate their use of 25-item career management strategies and also any other strategies they use, which were not offered on the list. Respondents rated each strategy on a scale ranging from 1 ("Not at all used") to 5 ("Used to a great extent"). Appendix 1 shows the strategies used by the respondents. The total measure had a standardised Cronbach's alpha reliability of 0.776. Four items were eliminated as their inter-item score correlation sums were less than 0.4. Those items were identified by "*" in Appendix 1. The remaining 21-item measure retained a reliability of 0.898.

Principal-components factor analysis (Varimax rotation) was conducted as a form of data reduction. The criteria adhered to are: Eigenvalues of all components should not be less than 1.0; the loadings should be 0.50 or greater to be considered practically significant; cronbach's alpha values of each factor extracted and overall measure should be greater than 0.7 (see Hair et al., 2006). Factor analysis yielded a set of four factors, which explained 70.45% of the variance. Factor 1 was labelled as “Self-presentation and extended work involvement”, Factor 2 as “Seek mentoring”, Factor 3 as “Networking”, and Factor 4 as “Expertise development and being flexible”. Table I shows the summarised results of the factor analysis.

Take in Table I

Job content plateau. Job content plateau was measured using six-item scale from McCleese and Eby (2006). Higher scores indicate greater perceptions of being job content plateaued. Factor analysis yielded one factor, where standardised Cronbach's alpha=.712 Eigenvalue=2.59, Explained variation=72.95%.

Hierarchical plateau. Hierarchical plateau was operationalized as the length of an employee's tenure in the current job. Veiga (1981) and Gould and Penley (1984) classified employees as hierarchical plateaued if tenure in their current position was seven or more years. We also considered IT professionals to be in a hierarchical career plateau if they had been in their current job for seven years or more. Of the 119 respondents, 64% was identified as not-plateaued (coded 0), and 36% was identified as plateaued (coded 1).

Firm and individual demographic characteristics. Firm size was assessed by the natural logarithmic transformation of the number of full-time employees in the organization. Age was measured in years. Gender (females=0, males=1) and marital status (single=0, married=1) were dichotomous variables.

The self-administered survey questionnaire was pre-tested with a random sample that fitted with the intended sample of the study prior to the distribution. Multiple regression was used to identify factors that predict career management strategies.

Results

Table II shows means, standard deviations and zero-order correlations among variables.

Take in Table II

The results of multiple regression analysis are shown in Table III. It is apparent that age ($p < 0.01$) and hierarchical plateau ($p < 0.001$) is significant in predicting “self-presentation and extended work involvement”. “Seek mentoring” is significantly predicted by age ($p < 0.05$), number of employees ($p < 0.05$), hierarchical plateau ($p < 0.01$), and job content plateau ($p < 0.01$). “Networking” is significantly predicted by gender ($p < 0.001$), where males use this strategy more than females. “Expertise development and being flexible” is predicted by marital status ($p < 0.05$), age ($p < 0.05$), number of employees ($p < 0.01$), and hierarchical plateau ($p < 0.001$).

It is apparent from Table III that career management strategies are mostly used by those who were not in hierarchical plateau, i.e., IT professionals with less than seven years of tenure in the job. Therefore H1 is not supported. Job content plateau significantly predicts only the use of “seek mentoring”, and individuals’ who are not in job content plateau mostly use it. Therefore H2 is not supported. Gender significantly predicts only the use of “networking”, where males mostly use it than females, partially supporting H3. Further, three career management strategies (i.e., self-presentation and extended work involvement, seek mentoring, and expertise development and being flexible) are mostly used by older employees while “networking” is mostly used by younger employees than otherwise. This partially supports H4. Marital status

significantly predicts only the use of “expertise development and being flexible”, where single employees mostly use it than otherwise, partially supporting H5. Number of employees in the firm is significantly positively related only to “seek mentoring” and “expertise development and being flexible”, partially supporting H6.

Take in Table III

Discussion and concluding remarks

The study explored career management strategies used by IT professionals and evaluated those against hierarchical plateau, job content plateau, firm size, and individual demographic characteristics that may predict the use.

Four main career management strategies were identified. The career strategies of “seek mentoring” and “networking” involve working through or with other people. Literature suggests that interrelationships between individuals allow forming informal interactions and connections to people who already have influence (see Guthrie et al., 1998). However, previous research (such as Guthrie et al., 1998; Osnowitz, 2006; Kuijpers and Scheerens, 2006) emphasises the need of individuals having willingness and ability to communicate and interact with others to be successful in executing these strategies. On the other hand, the other two career management strategies, i.e., “self-presentation and extended work involvement” and “expertise development and being flexible”, do not demand a higher level of social element but demand more self or work orientation. In this regard, scholars (see van der Heijden, 2003) highlight the fact that being an expert and maintaining one's expertise is by no means an easy task. Specifically, new developments in the IT industry may cause changes in job content implying the need of updating the expertise of employees as well as developing new expertise to be effective in current and future work roles.

The low mean values for job content plateau (refer to Table II) suggest that IT professionals are not experiencing job content plateau. It could be due to the use of practices that facilitate lateral and cross-functional moves, which are widely used in IT industry that can prevent job content plateauing. Further, project based IT work environment could also facilitate in meeting both organisation's needs for flexibility and individual's need for broad-based career experiences. The findings of this study also led to reveal that the correlation between hierarchical plateau and job content plateau is weak and not significant, supporting the claims that hierarchical plateau may result in job content plateau though it is not a necessary consequence (see Nachbagauer and Riedl, 2002). Overall, job content plateau is found to be significantly related to the use of "seek mentoring".

It was found that the usefulness of a particular career management strategy significantly depends on hierarchical plateau. When vertical career movement is limited and position immobility has become a normal event in the OOITF (see Wickramasinghe, 2009), IT professionals have to stay in the same position longer period than expected. Such a circumstance is neither planned nor expected by individuals, yet, they have to react to this pressure by taking ownership of their own careers and responsibility for their own career development (also refer to Parry and Proctor-Thomson, 2003). This may have influenced them to execute career enhancing behaviours and activities.

It was also found that demographic characteristics (age, gender, and marital status), and firm size predicts certain career management strategies (refer to Table III). For instance, it was found that gender significantly predicts the use of "networking", where males mostly use it than females. This finding does not support Guthrie et al. (1998), who did not find differences by gender in the use of career management strategies. However, considerable further research is necessary to identify the potential of these variables in predicting career management strategies. The current study represents a step in that direction.

One of the interesting findings of the study is not only that hierarchical career plateau predicts significantly the use of career management strategies but also that these are mostly executed by individuals who are not in hierarchical plateau- in other words, IT professionals with less than seven years of tenure. This implies that IT professionals with less than seven years of tenure are more likely to engage in career management strategies since it gives them a sense of control over their careers and help them to plan their careers. On the other hand, this suggests that plateaued IT professionals (with seven years or more tenure) may not have become aware of the industry situation early in their IT careers as OoITF emerged as a promising industry in the country in late 1990s. Therefore, on one hand, those who have plateaued in their jobs have to take more control of their careers. On the other hand, employee career effectiveness will be greater when the individual and organization carry out their respective roles in career management (see Parry and Proctor-Thomson, 2003; Walker, 1989). However, a significant feature of offshore outsourced industry is the continuous search on the part of overseas clients for lower cost vendors/locations. Therefore, firms' preferred career management strategies could be tailored to meet business objectives conditioned by the global competitive environment. This may have influenced for the emergence of a short-term transactional deal between employees and employers (see Applebaum and Santiago, 1997). Yet, there is a need for firms to acknowledge and act upon their employees' careers, especially those who have plateaued in their jobs.

Limitations of the study and future research areas

Hierarchical career plateau was operationalised based on the objective measurement of years of tenure in the present job. Though this measure was widely used in the previous research, future studies could collect data on subjective measurement of hierarchical career plateau. Although the responsibility for career management lies with both individual and organization that employs them, this study was confined to individual led career management strategies. It is accepted that career management process involves

several other variables such as career exploration and career goals. Therefore, future studies could complement the findings by investigating those aspects of career management process.

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Tables

Table I: Summarised results of factor analysis

<i>Factor 1: Self-presentation and extended work involvement</i>	
Work hard when you know superiors will see results	.855
Work at your job beyond normal work hours	.639
Take your work home with you	.618
Present yourself as a person who “gets things done”	.860
Make your boss aware of assignments you want	.788
Make superior aware of accomplishments	.703
Assume leadership in work areas where there seems to be no leadership	.622
Explained variation	32.61%
Eigenvalue	6.52
Standardised Cronbach’s alpha	.828
<i>Factor 2: Seek mentoring</i>	
Get career guidance from experienced people in the organisation	.798
Get career guidance from supervisors	.764
Make your superiors aware of your career objectives	.691
Seek feedback about performance and implications for your progress	.672
Seek mentoring relationships	.645
Explained variation	16.98%
Eigenvalue	2.39
Standardised Cronbach’s alpha	.761
<i>Factor 3: Networking</i>	
Build a network of friendships in the organisation to help careers	.780
Build a network of contacts in the organisation to get information	.717
Get career guidance from people outside the organisation	.678
Explained variation	11.80%
Eigenvalue	1.56
Standardised Cronbach’s alpha	.776
<i>Factor 4: Expertise development and being flexible</i>	
Develop skills which may be needed in future career options	.622
Look for opportunities to learn new skills	.845
Obtain broadly based work experiences in the organisation	.727
Keep career options open	.717
Develop expertise in areas critical to the department’s operation	.698
Seek development opportunities (eg: seminars, classes) outside the organisation	.696
Explained variation	9.06%
Eigenvalue	1.41
Standardised Cronbach’s alpha	.738

Table II: Means, standard deviations and zero-order correlations

	Mean	S.D.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
1 Gender ^a	.64	.476	1								
2 Marital status ^a	.55	.491	.530**	1							
3 Age	31.36	2.48	.341**	.354**	1						
4 No. of employees ^b	6.49	.49	-.285**	-.278**	-.097	1					
5 Hierarchical plateau	.66	.43	.249**	.352**	.556**	-.067	1				
6 Job content plateau	2.76	.46	-.065	-.060	-.158*	-.024	.135*	1			
7 Self-presentation and extended work involvement	3.42	.57	-.056	.016	.244**	.084	-.558**	-.112	1		
8 Seek mentoring	3.74	.59	-.183*	.157*	.210*	.256**	-.286**	-.256**	.222**	1	
9 Networking	3.43	.81	.270**	-.024	.124	.142	-.146*	-.118	.299**	.091	1
10 Expertise development and being flexible	3.79	.53	.117	-.250**	.184*	.339**	-.420**	-.042	.244**	.248**	.156*

Note: ** significant at the 0.01 level (1-tailed); * significant at the 0.05 level (1-tailed).

^a Binary-coded variables.

^b Log transformed.

Table III: Summarised results of regression analysis

	Career management strategy			
	Self-presentation and extended work involvement	Seek mentoring	Networking	Expertise development and being flexible
Gender	-.048	-.148	.437***	.053
Marital status	.169	.061	-.079	-.268*
Age	.235**	.207*	.191	.199*
No. of employees	.054	.221*	.062	.242**
Hierarchical plateau	-.732***	-.335**	-.192	-.378***
Job content plateau	-.069	-.306**	-.155	-.002
Model R ² (Adj.)	.404***	.219***	.234***	.344***

Note: Standardised regression coefficients (betas) are reported.

* p<0.05, ** p<0.01, *** p<0.001

Figure

Figure I: Research model

Appendix I: Descriptive analysis - career management strategies

Career management strategy	Mean	S.D.
Seek feedback about performance and implications for your progress	4.08	0.81
Look for opportunities to learn new skills	4.08	0.88
Make your superiors aware of your career objectives	3.99	0.72
Adapt to changes in my work*	3.98	0.78
Develop skills which may be needed in future career options	3.97	0.85
Keep career options open	3.88	0.83
Develop expertise in areas critical to the department's operation	3.87	0.66
Make your boss aware of assignments you want	3.87	0.85
Obtain broadly based work experiences in the organization	3.87	0.68
Present yourself as a person who "gets things done"	3.82	0.76
Work hard when you know superiors will see results	3.80	0.85
Adapt to changes in who I work with*	3.79	0.79
Get career guidance from supervisors	3.77	0.73
Build a network of contacts in the organization to get information	3.71	0.89
Make superior aware of accomplishments	3.70	0.60
Assume leadership in work areas where there seems to be no leadership	3.55	0.99
Build a network of friendships in the organization to help careers	3.51	0.89
Seek mentoring relationships	3.46	0.87
Get career guidance from experienced people in the organization	3.42	1.12
Attend organization development opportunities*	3.35	0.89
Work at your job beyond normal work hours	3.23	1.14
Seek development opportunities outside the organization	3.11	1.20
Get career guidance from people outside the organization	3.08	1.22
Take your work home with you	2.91	1.09
Spend considerable non-work hours thinking about your job*	2.04	1.26

Note: * the item was dropped during factor analysis